

Research Publication Trends among Physicists of the Indian Institute of Science and the University of Kerala: A Bibliometric Study

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ABSTRACT

The bibliometric study analysed the research productivity of physicists at the Indian Institute of Science (IISc) and the University of Kerala (KU) during 2004–2008. The paper gives a summary and review of the various research evaluation studies of institutions and disciplines. There were 352 research articles listed in the Physics doctoral theses of both the institutions, including 267 from the IISc and 85 from the KU. The authorship trend is towards multi-authored papers in IISc and solo research is predominant in the KU. The degree of collaboration of publication was calculated to be 0.94 in IISc researchers and 0.40 in the case of the KU. Journals are the most preferred channel of publication of IISc researchers while KU researchers prefer to publish their research findings mostly in national seminars. The study shows that the Phys. Rev. B tops the list of IISc physicists' choice of journals for publication with 16 publications (9.58%). The KU researchers prefer to publish their research results mostly in Indian journal of Radio and Space Physics with 10 articles 25.64%. Elsevier Science publisher is the most common publisher preferred by the Physicists of both institutions.

KeyTerms: Bibliometrics, Research Publications, Physicists, Indian Institute of Science, University of Kerala, Authorship Study, Doctoral Thesis.

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INTRODUCTION

Physics research in India is basically an institutional activity, pursued countrywide with funding coming from several sectors including academic, R & D, government and industry. The academic sector constitutes universities, institutions of higher learning, and colleges. There are nearly 435 Physics based research institutions in the country employing more than 5000 Ph.Ds and several thousands masters' engaged in research programmes in the major areas of Physics. A large number of universities are engaged in post graduate teaching and research and doctoral programmes. As a result, around 7000 PhDs are awarded each year in Physics, Dhawan et.al. (2007). Even though Physics institutions are spread throughout India, the research activity in Physics is confined mainly to select few institutions only in the country. According to Boyer (1973), the research process is incomplete if the research results are not used or not made readily accessible to the potentially interested researchers. These institutions are regarded as R & D leaders in this area. The Indian Institute of Science (IISc), Bangalore comes under this category of institution.

Bibliometrics is emerged as a research front in its own right in information science. It is now being vigorously pursued and with

the result, it has been found that one-fourth of all the articles published in Library and Information Science periodicals are on bibliometrics and its related topics. It has also been found that many of the Social Science and Science periodicals are also carrying a large number of articles on Bibliometrics, Maheswarappa (1997). Bibliometrics is a set of methods used to study or measure texts and information. Citation analysis and content analysis are commonly used bibliometric methods. While bibliometric methods are most often used in the field of library and information science, bibliometrics have wide applications in other areas. In fact, many research fields use bibliometric methods to explore the impact of their field, the impact of a set of researchers, or the impact of a particular paper. Bibliometrics are now used in quantitative research assessment exercises of academic output which is starting to threaten practice based research.

Indian Institute of Science (IISc) is particularly selected for comparison because of its national importance as a Centre of Excellence in Physics. The World Education report ranks the Bangalore based institute as the 18th best academic centre of the world. Since it emerged out of Jamshed Ji Tata's vision in 1909, it has grown into an advanced research and education centre, indeed, a premier 'brain trust' of the country. IISc has celebrated

its centenary in 2009. Its character, which blends the ambience of a University with the advantage of a research institution, has helped IISc to maintain a steady level of academic performance. The Department of Physics established by the Nobel laureate Sir. C.V. Raman in 1933 is the oldest division of Physical and Mathematical Sciences. Since 1998 the largest number 110 PhDs in Physics in India come from this department.

University of Kerala, which occupies the position of the mother university in the state, has been at the centre of all higher education activity in Kerala since its very inception. The University of Travancore which eventually became the University of Kerala was established in 1937 by a promulgation of the Maharaja of Travancore Sri Chithira Tirunal Balarama Varma, was transferred in to the present name in 1957. The Department of Physics was formally established in 1970 by Prof. K. S. Viswanathan.

In the present study an attempt has been made to study the scholarly research contributions of the physicists of IISc and KU during the period of their research and the lists are included in their doctoral dissertations. Dissertations are current, impartial reviews with extensive references and most of them contains list of research publications of the researchers and the supervising teachers. Cito analytical studies of doctoral dissertations, which are the products of research activity, form an important source of information.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A number of quantitative studies based on bibliometric/scientometric techniques have been reported to evaluate the research productivity of individuals, institutions, countries etc. Bibliometric studies based on dissertations have been carried out in India and abroad, in order to understand the pattern of materials used by the scientists for their research purposes in different branches of science during the last two decades.

Chandra Arya (2012), studied the authorship pattern and collaborative research trends in the field of Veterinary Medicine based on the data collected from Indian journal of Veterinary Medicine. Sudhier et.al. (2011) analysed the research productivity of social scientists at the Centre for development Studies, Trivandrum during 1998-2008. There were 599 research articles published by the CDS researchers. Jeyshankar et.al. (2011) analysed bibliographical details of 1282 research articles published by the scientists of CECRI during the period 2000-2009. Sahu et.al. (2011), studied the research publication trend of National Metallurgical Laboratory during the year 2001- 2010 based on the data obtained from Science Citation Index (SCI).

Nandi et.al. (2010) studied research productivity in Zoology by analysing 719 articles submitted by the scholars of the Zoology Department of the University of Burdwan. Bala et.al. (2010), in their study attempted to analyse the research profile of biochemistry, genetics and molecular biology research in India during 1998-2007. Sudhier (2010), in his scientometric study analysed the publications of Physics researchers at the Indian Institute of Science.

Scientometric analysis of 67 theses and 610 articles (based on theses submitted by the scholars during 1960-2000 in the Dept. of Physics at the University of Burdwan) scattered in 8 subdivisions of Physics were analysed by Nandi et.al. (2009). Bala et.al.

(2009), studied the research output of Govt. Medical College and Hospital, Chandigarh. Girap et.al. (2009) in their scientometric study analysed the publication productivity of the Technical Physics and Prototype Engineering Division at Bhabha Atomic Research Centre. Research articles published by the scientists of central Potato research Institute, Shimla during 1991-2007 were studied by Sharma (2009).

The impact and growth of research output of the various departments of the University of Mysore during 1996-2006 was conducted by Kubar et.al. (2008). Sevukan et.al. (2008), presented a detailed analysis of research performance of Biotechnology faculties in central universities of India from 1997-2006. Scientometric analysis of 1044 papers published by the scientists of Radiochemistry Division at Bhabha Atomic Research Centre (BARC) during 1958-2005 was done by, Kademani et.al. (2007). Sudhier (2007) studied 690 journal citations collected from the doctoral theses of IISc during five year period and was observed that journals are the most frequently bibliographic form of citations.

Gopikuttan (2004) in his scientometric study dealt with the research output in terms of journal articles, reports, books etc produced by the teachers of Science Departments, Faculty of Science, University of Kerala between 1980 and 1999 (20 Years). Jeevan et.al. (2002) in their scientometric study analysed the research profile of IIT, Kharagpur. Soman (2001) as part of his doctoral research programme, attempted to assess the scientific information productivity of physical scientists in the universities in Kerala, and to find out the factors that affect the scientific information productivity and to examine the role of information technology in augmenting the scientific productivity of the physical scientists.

Garg et.al. (1998) made a scientometric analysis of the publication data of the scientists of an Indian Physics laboratory (New Delhi). Authors found that the scientists preferred to publish their communications in foreign journals included in the SCI. Sangam et.al. (1997), studied the trends in Physics research publication and institutions wise contribution to the Physics research publications by analysing the research publications reported in Indian Science Abstract.

Even though several studies have done to study the scientific productivity of scientists in the country, no studies have been made for the comparative evaluation of the research contributions of physicists of two institutions based on the publications included in the doctoral dissertations. Hence this study is carried out.

OBJECTIVES

The main purpose of the study is to examine the publication productivity of physicists of IISc and KU during the period 2004-08 as indicated in the doctoral dissertations. The objectives include:

- ❑ To study the research publication productivity of Physicists
- ❑ To ascertain the authorship and collaboration pattern of researchers
- ❑ To examine the communication channels preferred by the Physicists

- ❑ To prepare a rank list of journals preferred for publication
- ❑ To find out country wise distribution of journals

METHODOLOGY

Bibliometric analysis of 352 scholarly publications appended in the Physics doctoral thesis of researchers of IISc and KU, are collected for the five years period. Out of 352 publications, 267 are from the IISc and 85 from the KU doctoral theses. All the bibliographic details of publications were collected and analysed based on the bibliometric techniques like publication productivity, authorship trend, ranked journals, and communication channels preferred etc. as per the objectives of the study.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

❑ Number of Publications

A comparative analysis of number of publications included in the doctoral dissertations of IISc and the University of Kerala physicists are included in the table 1.

Table 1: Number of Publications

Publications	IISc		KU		Total	
	Count	%age	Count	%age	Count	%age
Nil	39	54.9	1	8.3	40	48.2
1-5	6	8.5	3	25.0	9	10.9
6-10	18	25.4	6	50.0	24	28.9
11-15	8	11.2	2	16.7	10	12.0
Total	71	100	12	100	83	100

It is observed that 39 (54.9%) researchers of IISc do not include the list of publications in their theses. Whereas in the University of Kerala, almost of thesis 11 include the list of publications except one. The highest number of thesis 25.4% are having 6-10 publications and 6 theses have 1-5 range of publications in IISc theses. While 6 thesis 50% have 6-10 range of publications and three theses have 1-5 range of publications in the case of KU.

❑ Average Number of Publications

Table 2 shows the comparison of average number of publications per theses of the two institutions.

Table 2: Average Number of Publications

Institution	Mean	SD	t	p
IISc	3.7	4.7	2.50	p<0.01
KU	6.8	3.6		

The average number of publication per theses in IISc is 3.7 with a Standard Deviation (SD) 4.7 and the average number of publication per thesis in KU is 6.8 with a SD 3.6. The t-statistics is 2.5 with a p value less than 0.01. It means that the average number of publications per thesis is statistically high in KU

compared to IISc. This may because of the non inclusion of list of publications of IISc researchers in their theses.

❑ Year wise Distribution of Average Number of Publications

The table 3 shows the year wise comparison of average number of publications of IISc and KU scholars during the period of study.

Table 3: Year Wise Analysis of Average Number of Publications

Institutions	Year	Mean	SD	F	P
IISc	2004	3.4	5.0	0.7	p>0.05
	2005	3.2	3.6		
	2006	5.2	4.9		
	2007	2.5	4.1		
	2008	3.3	5.5		
KU	2005	6.7	1.2	2.8	p>0.05
	2007	4.0	3.3		
	2008	9.0	3.7		

In the case of IISc, the average number of publication is high 5.2 in 2006 with standard deviation 4.9 and a minimum 2.5 in 2007 with standard deviation 4.1. The F-value is 0.7 with a p value greater than 0.05. It means that, statistically there is no significance in the number of publication in different years.

While in the KU, the average number of publications is maximum (9.0) in 2008 with standard deviation 3.7 and a minimum 4.0 in 2007 with standard deviation 3.3. The F-value is 2.8 with a p value greater than 0.05. It also shows the year wise analysis is statistically insignificant. The analysis also revealed that, no theses were awarded during the years 2004 and 2006.

❑ Gender wise Productivity of Research Publications

Table 4 shows the gender-wise distribution of publications of physicists of the two institutions

Table 4: Gender-Wise Analysis of Research Publications

Year	IISc		KU		Total
	Male	Female	Male	Female	
2004	61	11	0	0	72
2005	33	2	15	6	56
2006	75	30	0	0	105
2007	18	7	0	17	42
2008	16	14	32	15	77
Total	203	64	47	38	352

In Table 4, out of the 267 publications of IISc scholars, majority of 203 publications are the contributions of male scholars and 64 are of female scholars. This is because of the dominance of male researchers of IISc. While in KU, the scene is different. Even though the theses productivity of female scholars are more than that of males, the productivity of research publications are more for male scholars. It is seen from the analysis that the contributions of male scholars are 45 publications, where as female scholars contribute 36 articles during the period.

Gender-wise Average Number of Publication Productivity

Comparative analysis of average number of publications of male and female scholars is shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Gender Wise Analysis of Average Number of Publications

Institutions	Sex	Mean	SD	t	P
IISc	Male	3.9	4.6	0.41	p>0.05
	Female	3.4	4.9		
KU	Male	9.0	3.5	2.07	p>0.05
	Female	5.1	3.0		

The analysis shows that the average number of publications of male scholars of IISc is 3.9 with standard deviation 4.6 and that of female scholars is 3.4 with a standard deviation 0.49 with a p value greater than 0.05. It shows that the difference of average number of publication of male and female scholars of IISc is statistically not significant. While in the KU, the average number of publications of male scholars is 9.0 with a standard deviation 3.5 and for female scholars it is 5.1 with a standard deviation of 3.0. The t-statistics is 2.07 with a p value greater than 0.05. It also shows that comparison is statistically insignificant.

Authorship Pattern of Publications

Table 6: Authorship Pattern of Publications

Authors	IISc		KU		Chi-square	P
	Count	%age	Count	%age		
1	16	5.99	51	60.0	134.13	p<0.01
2	55	20.60	19	22.4		
3	42	15.73	7	8.2		
4	59	22.10	3	3.5		
5+	95	35.58	5	5.9		
Total	267	100	85	100		

The authorship trend is towards multi-authored papers in IISc and solo research is predominant in the KU. In IISc, single authored papers account for 5.99% (16) followed by two authored papers 20.60% (55) and three authored papers 15.73% (42). The trend is different in the University of Kerala. Single authored papers account for 60% (51) and the remaining 40% (34) are multi-

authored, of which 22.4% (19) are joint authorship papers.

Chi-Square test is applied to the data and the value of χ^2 is found to be 134.13 with a p-value less than 0.01, which is highly significant. The Chi-square test proves the difference of authorship pattern of two institutions is statistically significant.

Average Number of Authors of Publications

Table 7: Average Number of Authors of Publications

Institutions	Mean	SD	n	t	Sig.
IISc	4.0	2.1	267	12.66	0.00
KU	1.7	1.1	85		

Table 7 depicts the average number of authors per article of IISc researchers is found to be 4 and it is 1.7 in the KU. The result of the t-test is 12.66 at 0.00 significance level and it indicates that the average number of authors per article of IISc researchers is significantly very high. The result indicates that the publications of IISc researchers are multi-authored papers compared to the publications of K researchers. Hence the result is statistically significant.

Degree of Collaboration of Publications

Table 8: Degree of Collaboration of Publications

IISc			KU		
Single Authors	Multiple Authors	Degree of Collaboration	Single Authors	Multiple Authors	Degree of Collaboration
16	251	0.94	51	34	0.40

The table 8 indicates that 251 (94%) of the publication of IISc researchers are multi-authored and only 16 (6%) are single contribution. The degree of collaboration is calculated as 0.94. The results of the analysis show that collaborative results are prevalent in IISc Physics labs. While 51 (60%) publications of the KU researchers are single authored contributions and the remaining 34 (40%) are multi-authored publications. The degree of collaboration is estimated as 0.40. In this case single authored publications are more, and therefore solo research may be prominent in Department of Physics, University of Kerala.

Communication Channels Preferred for Publication

Table 9: Channels of Publications of Physicists

Category	IISc		KU	
	Count	%age	Count	%age
Journals	131	49.1	20	23.5
Communicated	53	19.9	19	22.4
International Seminars	30	11.2	6	7.1
National Seminars	27	10.1	37	43.4
Manuscripts	23	8.6	0	0
Technical Reports	2	0.7	0	0
Books	1	0.4	2	2.4
Patent	0	0	1	1.2
Total	267	100	85	100

As depicts in the table 9 the journals are the most preferred channel of publication of IISc scholars and it amounts 49.1% (131) of all publications. 19.9% (53) articles are in the form of communicated category and are not published yet. The international seminar category accounts 11.2% (30) and only 1 (0.4%) publication is in the form of book. It is interesting to see that patents are not in the publication list. KU scholars prefer to publish their research findings in national seminars and it accounts 43.4% (37) of total publications. The second position goes to the journals 23.5% and communicated category accounts 22.4% (19). The technical report's and manuscripts are not included in the publication list.

□ Choice of Journals for Publication

From the previous analysis it can be seen that table 9 the journals are the most preferred channel of publication of IISc scholars 49% and in the University of Kerala it occupies the second position with 23.5% of total publications. The rank list of the most preferred journals by the Physicists of IISc are presented in the table 10. The journals preferred more than 4 times are included in the table 10.

Table 10: Ranked Journals for Publication (IISc)

Journal	Country*	Rank	Count	%age	Cum %	IF**
Phys.Rev.B	USA	1	16	9.58	9.58	3.075
J.Crystal Growth	Netherland	2	8	4.79	14.37	1.707
J.Phys-Condensed Matter	UK	2	8	4.79	19.16	2.049
Liq.Cryst.	UK	3	7	4.19	23.35	
Solid State Commun.	UK	3	7	4.19	27.54	1.523
Phys.Rev. Lett.	USA	4	6	3.59	31.14	7.218
App.Phys. Lett.	USA	5	5	2.99	34.13	4.308
Bull.of Astron Soc.	India	5	5	2.99	37.13	
Chem.Phys. Lett	Netherland	5	5	2.99	40.12	2.438
Euro.Phys. Lett.	France	5	5	2.99	43.11	2.120
J.Appl. Phys.	USA	5	5	2.99	46.11	2.255
Acta Cryst.	Denmark	6	4	2.40	48.50	1.829
Astro. and Astrophys.	France	6	4	2.40	50.90	3.694
Astrophysical J.	USA	6	4	2.40	53.29	6.237
Mon.Not. Roy. Astr.Soc.	UK	6	4	2.40	55.69	5.238
Phys.Rev.A	USA	6	4	2.40	58.08	2.902

* Data from Ulrich ** Data from JCR-2008

In the rank list, the Phys.Rev. B published by the American Physical Society (APS), tops with the highest contribution of 16 (9.58%) publications followed by Journal of crystal growth and Journal of Physics Condensed matter with 8 publications each, hold the second position 4.79%. Liquid crystals and Solid state communication with seven publications 4.19% each occupies third position. The choice of journals preferred for publications by the scholars of University of Kerala are shown in the table 11.

Table 11: Ranked List of Journals for Publication (KU)

Journal	Country*	Rank	Count	%age	Cum %	IF**
Ind. J. of Radio & Space Phys.	India	1	10	25.64	25.64	
J.Am.Ceram. Soc.	USA	2	4	10.26	35.90	0.401
Ind.J.of Phys.	India	3	3	7.69	43.59	
Spectrochim Acta, Part A	UK	3	3	7.69	51.28	1.188
U.Sci.Phyl. Sci.	France	3	3	7.69	58.97	
Ind.J.Pure. Appl.Phys.	India	4	2	5.13	64.10	0.088
Proc.Ind. Acad.Sci.	India	4	2	5.13	69.23	

* Data from Ulrich ** Data from JCR-2008

The journals preferred more than two times are given in the Table 11. Indian JI. of Radio and Space Physics published by the CSIR scores the top with 10 articles 25.64%, followed by Journal of American Ceramic society with 4 (10.26%) publications. The journals, Indian JI. of Physics, Spectrochim Act Part A and Ultra Sci. Phy. Science occupies the 3rd position with 3 (7.69%) articles each.

□ Country Wise Distribution of Journals

Table 12: Country Wise Distribution of Journals (IISc)

Country	Rank	Count	%age	Cum %
USA	1	66	43.42	43.42
UK	2	38	25	68.42
Netherland	3	19	12.50	80.92
India	4	10	6.58	87.50
Germany	5	6	3.95	91.45
France	6	5	3.29	94.74
Swiss	6	5	3.29	98.03
Denmark	7	2	1.31	99.34
Singapore	8	1	0.66	100
Total		152	100	

The analysis shows that USA, UK, Netherlands and India retain the first, second, third and fourth position in the ranking order respectively with 66 (43.42%), 38 (25%), 19 (12.5%) and 10 (6.58%) publications.

Table 13: Country Wise Distribution of Journals (KU)

Country	Rank	Count	%age	Cum %
India	1	21	58.3	58.33
USA	2	8	22.2	80.56
UK	3	3	8.3	88.89
Netherland	4	2	5.6	94.44
Singapore	5	1	2.8	97.22
Swiss	5	1	2.8	100
Total		36	100	

While in the University of Kerala the rank order is different. India retains the first position carrying 21 publications 58.3% followed by USA with 8 publications 22.2% and UK with 3 publications 8.3%.

Country of Origin

The bar diagram showing the country of origin of journals are shown in the Figure 1. It can be clearly seen that the KU scholars mostly preferred Indian journals and American journals are the most preferred journals of IISc researchers.

Diversity of Journals

Table 14: Language Wise Distribution of Journals

Language	IISc		KU	
	Count	% age	Count	%age
English	138	90.79	35	94.6
Dutch	13	8.55	2	5.4
French	1	0.66	0	0.0
Total	152	100	37	100

The study shows that English is the most widely used medium of correspondence for publication of Physicists of both institutions. While 138 (90.79%) publications of IISc scholars are in English, 35 (94.6%) publications of University of Kerala scholars prefers English. 8.55% of IISc publications are in Dutch language journals and 5.4% publications of KU scholars prefer it. The analysis also shows that one article of IISc scholar is in French journals.

Preferred Publishers

Table 15: Publishers of Journals (IISc)

Publisher	Rank	Count	%age	Cum %
APS	1	27	17.65	17.65
Elsevier Science	2	16	10.46	28.10
AIP	3	13	8.50	36.60
North Holland	3	13	8.50	45.10
IOP	4	11	7.19	52.29
AAS	5	7	4.58	56.86
Taylor & Francis	5	7	4.58	61.44
Academic Press	6	5	3.27	64.71
EDP Science	6	5	3.27	67.97
IAS	6	5	3.27	71.24
Kluwer	6	5	3.27	74.51
Wiley-VCH	6	5	3.27	77.78

The table 15 indicates that, the IISc scholars prefer to publish their articles in American Physical Society (APS) journals with 27 (17.65%) publications followed by Elsevier Science publishers with 16(10.46%) publications. This is followed by American Institute of Physics (AIP) and North-Holland comes in the third position with 13 publications 8.5% each.

Table 16: Publishers of Journals (KU)

Publisher	Rank	Count	%age	Cum %
CSIR	1	12	34.3	34.29
ACS	2	4	11.4	45.71
Elsevier Science	3	3	8.6	54.29
IACS	3	3	8.6	62.86
Kluwer	3	3	8.6	71.43
Pergamon	3	3	8.6	80.00
NAS	4	2	5.7	85.71

The Physicists of the KU prefer to publish their articles in CSIR journals, as seen in the table 16. It amounts 12 (34.3%) of the total publishers of journals. American Chemical Society (ACS) with 4 publications 11.4% comes second position and the following four publishers with 3 articles 8.60% shares the third position. They are Elsevier Science, IAC, Kluwer Academic Press, and Pergamon Press.

CONCLUSION

Publication productivity is the measure of the relationship between the output of research and inputs. Evaluating the productivity of an institutional research and development activities highlights the contribution of the institution and the individual scientists engaged in research. It also provides some insights into the complex dynamics of research activity and enables policy makers and administrators to provide adequate facilities and gauge the research activities in a proper direction. Over the years, scientometric and bibliometric techniques have become tools to evaluate the productivity of research institutes and individual researcher, as well as to map the growth of the research area.

There were 352 research articles listed in the Physics doctoral theses of IISc and KU, including 267 from the IISc and 85 from the KU. The average number of publications per theses of IISc theses is 3.7 while it is higher, 6.8 in the University of Kerala. Publications produced by male scholars are predominantly higher than that of female scholars of IISc. The authorship trend is towards multi-authored papers in IISc and solo research is predominant in the University of Kerala. The analysis reveals that the authorship pattern of two institutions is significantly different. The average number of authors per article of IISc researchers is 4 and it is 1.7 in the University of Kerala. The degree of collaboration of publication is calculated to be 0.94 in IISc researchers and 0.40 in the case of the University of Kerala.

Journals are the most preferred channel of publication of IISc researchers while the KU researchers prefer to publish their research findings mostly in seminars. The study shows that the Phys. Rev. B tops the list of IISc physicists choice of journals for publication with 16 publications 9.58%. The KU researchers prefer to publish their research articles mostly in Indian journal of Radio and Space Physics and it publishes 10 articles 25.64%. The publication behaviour of IISc physicists indicates that they are highly selective in publishing their research results in specialised journals with high IF.

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